

Different Types of Multiple Style Magic Squares of Order 28

Inder J. Taneja¹

Abstract

*Author worked on different kinds of magic squares. These include **block-wise**, **bordered**, **block-bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares. The **block-wise bordered** magic squares are very much similar to **bordered** magic squares, where the numbers are replaced by **blocks** of magic squares. For details refer author's work. It brings multiples blocks of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 and 14. This work brings different types of magic squares of order 28. It is a combination of **block-wise**, **bordered**, **block-bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares. For previous works from orders 10 to 26, 30, 36 and 40 refer author's work [32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37]. It is revised and extended version of author's previous work with corrections. The previous work was only with 102 magic squares of order 28. Total there are 238 different types of magic squares of order 28 given in this work. This paper is with few examples. The completed examples with **pdf files** are available at author's web-sites [3, 4].*

¹Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012).
Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976-1978).
E-mail: ijaneja@gmail.com; **Web-sites:** <http://inderjtaneja.com>;
Twitter: @IJTANEJA; **Instagram:** @crazynumbers.

Contents

1 Introduction	2
2 Magic Squares of Order 28	8
3 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation of Numbers	20

1 Introduction

The magic sums of order n of consecutive numbers from 1 to n^2 is given by

$$S_{n \times n} := \frac{n \times (1 + n^2)}{2}, n \geq 3. \quad (1)$$

This formula is applied to all order magic squares. Based on this formula we can easily check the possibilities of blocks of equal or unequal sums to construct **block-wise** magic squares. On the other side there are **bordered** magic squares. It is always possible to construct any order **bordered** magic squares, but the **block-wise** magic squares are not possible to construct always, for examples, magic squares of orders 10, 11, 13, 14, 17, 19, 22, 23, 26, etc. These are the cases of orders known by **p** and **2p**, where **p** is a **prime number**. These types of orders are constructed as **block-bordered** magic squares. There are four different kinds of magic squares. These four types are **block-wise**, **bordered**, **block-bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares. Below are few details of author's work on these four types:

1. **Block-Wise:** Below are two examples of **block-wise** magic squares of order 12.

98	1	51	72	22	119	78	28	125	140	43	93
3	50	97	118	71	24	124	77	30	45	92	139
49	99	2	23	120	70	29	126	76	91	141	44
131	34	84	87	37	134	57	7	104	113	16	66
36	83	130	133	86	39	103	56	9	18	65	112
82	132	35	38	135	85	8	105	55	64	114	17
67	117	20	5	102	52	47	144	94	73	123	26
21	68	115	100	53	6	142	95	48	27	74	121
116	19	69	54	4	101	96	46	143	122	25	75
88	138	41	32	129	79	14	111	61	58	108	11
42	89	136	127	80	33	109	62	15	12	59	106
137	40	90	81	31	128	63	13	110	107	10	60

7	140	1	142	15	132	9	134	23	124	17	126
2	141	8	139	10	133	16	131	18	125	24	123
144	3	138	5	136	11	130	13	128	19	122	21
137	6	143	4	129	14	135	12	121	22	127	20
31	116	25	118	39	108	33	110	47	100	41	102
26	117	32	115	34	109	40	107	42	101	48	99
120	27	114	29	112	35	106	37	104	43	98	45
113	30	119	28	105	38	111	36	97	46	103	44
55	92	49	94	63	84	57	86	71	76	65	78
50	93	56	91	58	85	64	83	66	77	72	75
96	51	90	53	88	59	82	61	80	67	74	69
89	54	95	52	81	62	87	60	73	70	79	68

More details on **block-wise** magic squares from orders 12 to 45 can be seen in author's work [5, 6, 7, 8, 10, 11].

2. **Bordered:** The **bordered** magic squares are extensively studied by H. White [1]. These constructions are by use of programming developed by H. White [1]. See below two examples of orders 10 and 12.

91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92
13	26	20	80	82	69	31	71	25	88
89	23	64	62	35	68	36	38	78	12
11	24	34	49	54	43	56	67	77	90
96	29	40	44	55	50	53	61	72	5
1	79	42	58	45	52	47	59	22	100
93	74	60	51	48	57	46	41	27	8
7	73	63	39	66	33	65	37	28	94
95	76	81	21	19	32	70	30	75	6
9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10

134	143	3	141	5	1	22	124	20	126	18	133
16	113	108	38	106	40	36	26	120	24	114	129
15	35	48	42	102	104	91	53	93	47	110	130
131	111	45	86	84	57	90	58	60	100	34	14
132	33	46	56	71	76	65	78	89	99	112	13
139	118	51	62	66	77	72	75	83	94	27	6
128	23	101	64	80	67	74	69	81	44	122	17
10	115	96	82	73	70	79	68	63	49	30	135
9	29	95	85	61	88	55	87	59	50	116	136
137	117	98	103	43	41	54	92	52	97	28	8
7	31	37	107	39	105	109	119	25	121	32	138
12	2	142	4	140	144	123	21	125	19	127	11

More details can be seen in author’s work [12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18]. Also refer H. Danielsson [2].

3. **Block-Bordered:** The **block-bordered** magic squares are magic squares where we are unable to work with **block-wise** magic squares. These magic squares are of orders **p** or **2p**, where **p** is a prime number. For example, magic squares of orders 10, 11, 13, 14, etc. In this case we write only external border and the inner parts are constructed as **blocks**. See below two examples of orders 10 and 14:

91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92
13	47	58	19	78	39	66	27	70	88
89	22	75	50	55	30	67	42	63	12
11	82	23	54	43	74	31	62	35	90
96	51	46	79	26	59	38	71	34	5
1	48	57	20	77	40	65	28	69	100
93	21	76	49	56	29	68	41	64	8
7	81	24	53	44	73	32	61	36	94
95	52	45	80	25	60	37	72	33	6
9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10

14	8	188	10	186	12	196	7	182	16	180	18	178	184
195	33	166	27	168	41	158	35	160	49	150	43	152	2
3	28	167	34	165	36	159	42	157	44	151	50	149	194
193	170	29	164	31	162	37	156	39	154	45	148	47	4
5	163	32	169	30	155	40	161	38	147	48	153	46	192
191	57	142	51	144	65	134	59	136	73	126	67	128	6
177	52	143	58	141	60	135	66	133	68	127	74	125	20
171	146	53	140	55	138	61	132	63	130	69	124	71	26
25	139	56	145	54	131	64	137	62	123	72	129	70	172
173	81	118	75	120	89	110	83	112	97	102	91	104	24
23	76	119	82	117	84	111	90	109	92	103	98	101	174
175	122	77	116	79	114	85	108	87	106	93	100	95	22
21	115	80	121	78	107	88	113	86	99	96	105	94	176
13	189	9	187	11	185	1	190	15	181	17	179	19	183

For more details see authors work [19, 20, 11].

4. **block-wise** and **block-bordered** magic squares are the combinations of the items 1, 2 and 3. Still we can write magic squares as blocks of **bordered** magic squares. See the examples below:

14	8	188	10	186	12	196	7	182	16	180	18	178	184
195	166	164	29	170	30	32	148	146	47	152	48	50	2
3	28	43	156	37	158	169	46	61	138	55	140	151	194
193	34	38	157	44	155	163	52	56	139	62	137	145	4
5	36	160	39	154	41	161	54	142	57	136	59	143	192
191	162	153	42	159	40	35	144	135	60	141	58	53	6
177	165	33	168	27	167	31	147	51	150	45	149	49	20
171	112	110	83	116	84	86	130	128	65	134	66	68	26
25	82	97	102	91	104	115	64	79	120	73	122	133	172
173	88	92	103	98	101	109	70	74	121	80	119	127	24
23	90	106	93	100	95	107	72	124	75	118	77	125	174
175	108	99	96	105	94	89	126	117	78	123	76	71	22
21	111	87	114	81	113	85	129	69	132	63	131	67	176
13	189	9	187	11	185	1	190	15	181	17	179	19	183

8	2	254	256	243	13	245	7	40	34	222	224	211	45	213	39
5	238	236	17	242	18	20	252	37	206	204	49	210	50	52	220
6	16	31	228	25	230	241	251	38	48	63	196	57	198	209	219
11	22	26	229	32	227	235	246	43	54	58	197	64	195	203	214
253	24	232	27	226	29	233	4	221	56	200	59	194	61	201	36
248	234	225	30	231	28	23	9	216	202	193	62	199	60	55	41
247	237	21	240	15	239	19	10	215	205	53	208	47	207	51	42
250	255	3	1	14	244	12	249	218	223	35	33	46	212	44	217
104	98	158	160	147	109	149	103	72	66	190	192	179	77	181	71
101	142	140	113	146	114	116	156	69	174	172	81	178	82	84	188
102	112	127	132	121	134	145	155	70	80	95	164	89	166	177	187
107	118	122	133	128	131	139	150	75	86	90	165	96	163	171	182
157	120	136	123	130	125	137	100	189	88	168	91	162	93	169	68
152	138	129	126	135	124	119	105	184	170	161	94	167	92	87	73
151	141	117	144	111	143	115	106	183	173	85	176	79	175	83	74
154	159	99	97	110	148	108	153	186	191	67	65	78	180	76	185

For more details see the author's work [22, 23, 24, 25].

5. **Block-Wise Bordered:** The **block-wise bordered** magic squares are the extension of **bordered** magic squares. In case of **bordered** magic squares, the borders are formed by numbers, while in case of **block-wise bordered** magic squares the external borders are formed by blocks. This means, when we remove external border, we are always left with magic squares with sequential entries. The same happens with **block-wise bordered** magic squares. In this case, the blocks are multiples of orders 4, 6, 8, etc. Sometimes, we call them as **multiple blocks** magic squares. See below the example of order 20:

7	396	1	398	15	388	9	390	23	380	17	382	31	372	25	374	39	364	33	366
2	397	8	395	10	389	16	387	18	381	24	379	26	373	32	371	34	365	40	363
400	3	394	5	392	11	386	13	384	19	378	21	376	27	370	29	368	35	362	37
393	6	399	4	385	14	391	12	377	22	383	20	369	30	375	28	361	38	367	36
127	276	121	278	135	268	129	270	143	260	137	262	151	252	145	254	47	356	41	358
122	277	128	275	130	269	136	267	138	261	144	259	146	253	152	251	42	357	48	355
280	123	274	125	272	131	266	133	264	139	258	141	256	147	250	149	360	43	354	45
273	126	279	124	265	134	271	132	257	142	263	140	249	150	255	148	353	46	359	44
119	284	113	286	191	212	185	214	199	204	193	206	159	244	153	246	55	348	49	350
114	285	120	283	186	213	192	211	194	205	200	203	154	245	160	243	50	349	56	347
288	115	282	117	216	187	210	189	208	195	202	197	248	155	242	157	352	51	346	53
281	118	287	116	209	190	215	188	201	198	207	196	241	158	247	156	345	54	351	52
111	292	105	294	183	220	177	222	175	228	169	230	167	236	161	238	63	340	57	342
106	293	112	291	178	221	184	219	170	229	176	227	162	237	168	235	58	341	64	339
296	107	290	109	224	179	218	181	232	171	226	173	240	163	234	165	344	59	338	61
289	110	295	108	217	182	223	180	225	174	231	172	233	166	239	164	337	62	343	60
103	300	97	302	95	308	89	310	87	316	81	318	79	324	73	326	71	332	65	334
98	301	104	299	90	309	96	307	82	317	88	315	74	325	80	323	66	333	72	331
304	99	298	101	312	91	306	93	320	83	314	85	328	75	322	77	336	67	330	69
297	102	303	100	305	94	311	92	313	86	319	84	321	78	327	76	329	70	335	68

The author worked in this direction for the **multiple blocks** magic squares of multiples of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 and 14. For more details refer author’s work [26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31].

This work is a combination of above five items resulting in **different types** of magic squares of order 32. There are total 238 magic squares of order 38. For previous works from orders 10 to 40 refer author's recent works [32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37]. The table below give numbers of magic squares for the orders 10 to 40.

Order of Magic Square	Number of Magic Squares
Order 10	3
Order 12	7
Order 14	8
Order 16	10
Order 18	13
Order 20	31
Order 22	31
Order 24	138
Order 26	138
Order 28	238
Order 30	110
Order 32	1309
Order 36	1949
Order 40	3557

This work is a combination of above five items resulting in different types of magic squares of order 28. There are total 238 magic squares of order 28. Due to high quantity, only few examples are written. The other examples can be seen in two **pdf files** at author's web-sites [3, 4].

2 Magic Squares of Order 28

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 28 is given by

$$S_{28 \times 28} := \frac{28 \times (1 + 28^2)}{2} = 10990.$$

We can write, $28 := 2 \times 2 \times 7$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 4, 7 and 14. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 10990 by 7 and 4:

$$(i) \quad \frac{10990}{7} = 1570 \implies \text{equal sum blocks of order 4;}$$
$$(iii) \quad \frac{10990}{4} = 2747.5 \implies \text{unequal sum blocks of order 7.}$$

Below are few different ways of writing magic squares of order 28. It includes **block-wise**, **bordered**, **block-bordered** and **mix styles**. By **mix style** we understand that the magic squares are with any style as cited above. In this case, we have written 238 different types of magic squares. Some of them are very much similar but are different. Below are few examples:

1.

7	780	1	782	15	772	9	774	23	764	17	766	31	756	25	758	39	748	33	750	47	740	41	742	55	732	49	734
2	781	8	779	10	773	16	771	18	765	24	763	26	757	32	755	34	749	40	747	42	741	48	739	50	733	56	731
784	3	778	5	776	11	770	13	768	19	762	21	760	27	754	29	752	35	746	37	744	43	738	45	736	51	730	53
777	6	783	4	769	14	775	12	761	22	767	20	753	30	759	28	745	38	751	36	737	46	743	44	729	54	735	52
191	596	185	598	199	588	193	590	207	580	201	582	215	572	209	574	223	564	217	566	231	556	225	558	63	724	57	726
186	597	192	595	194	589	200	587	202	581	208	579	210	573	216	571	218	565	224	563	226	557	232	555	58	725	64	723
600	187	594	189	592	195	586	197	584	203	578	205	576	211	570	213	568	219	562	221	560	227	554	229	728	59	722	61
593	190	599	188	585	198	591	196	577	206	583	204	569	214	575	212	561	222	567	220	553	230	559	228	721	62	727	60
183	604	177	606	319	468	313	470	327	460	321	462	335	452	329	454	343	444	337	446	239	548	233	550	71	716	65	718
178	605	184	603	314	469	320	467	322	461	328	459	330	453	336	451	338	445	344	443	234	549	240	547	66	717	72	715
608	179	602	181	472	315	466	317	464	323	458	325	456	331	450	333	448	339	442	341	552	235	546	237	720	67	714	69
601	182	607	180	465	318	471	316	457	326	463	324	449	334	455	332	441	342	447	340	545	238	551	236	713	70	719	68
175	612	169	614	311	476	305	478	383	404	377	406	391	396	385	398	351	436	345	438	247	540	241	542	79	708	73	710
170	613	176	611	306	477	312	475	378	405	384	403	386	397	392	395	346	437	352	435	242	541	248	539	74	709	80	707
616	171	610	173	480	307	474	309	408	379	402	381	400	387	394	389	440	347	434	349	544	243	538	245	712	75	706	77
609	174	615	172	473	310	479	308	401	382	407	380	393	390	399	388	433	350	439	348	537	246	543	244	705	78	711	76
167	620	161	622	303	484	297	486	375	412	369	414	367	420	361	422	359	428	353	430	255	532	249	534	87	700	81	702
162	621	168	619	298	485	304	483	370	413	376	411	362	421	368	419	354	429	360	427	250	533	256	531	82	701	88	699
624	163	618	165	488	299	482	301	416	371	410	373	424	363	418	365	432	355	426	357	536	251	530	253	704	83	698	85
617	166	623	164	481	302	487	300	409	374	415	372	417	366	423	364	425	358	431	356	529	254	535	252	697	86	703	84
159	628	153	630	295	492	289	494	287	500	281	502	279	508	273	510	271	516	265	518	263	524	257	526	95	692	89	694
154	629	160	627	290	493	296	491	282	501	288	499	274	509	280	507	266	517	272	515	258	525	264	523	90	693	96	691
632	155	626	157	496	291	490	293	504	283	498	285	512	275	506	277	520	267	514	269	528	259	522	261	696	91	690	93
625	158	631	156	489	294	495	292	497	286	503	284	505	278	511	276	513	270	519	268	521	262	527	260	689	94	695	92
151	636	145	638	143	644	137	646	135	652	129	654	127	660	121	662	119	668	113	670	111	676	105	678	103	684	97	686
146	637	152	635	138	645	144	643	130	653	136	651	122	661	128	659	114	669	120	667	106	677	112	675	98	685	104	683
640	147	634	149	648	139	642	141	656	131	650	133	664	123	658	125	672	115	666	117	680	107	674	109	688	99	682	101
633	150	639	148	641	142	647	140	649	134	655	132	657	126	663	124	665	118	671	116	673	110	679	108	681	102	687	100
Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@NumbersMagic															

26.

14	8	776	10	774	12	784	7	770	16	768	18	766	772	112	106	678	108	676	110	686	105	672	114	670	116	668	674																												
783	81	722	27	740	82	721	28	739	83	720	29	738	2	685	179	624	125	642	180	623	126	641	181	622	127	640	100																												
3	44	723	98	705	43	724	97	706	42	725	96	707	782	101	142	625	196	607	141	626	195	608	140	627	194	609	684																												
781	758	45	704	63	757	46	703	64	756	47	702	65	4	683	660	143	606	161	659	144	605	162	658	145	604	163	102																												
5	687	80	741	62	688	79	742	61	689	78	743	60	780	103	589	178	643	160	590	177	644	159	591	176	645	158	682																												
779	84	719	30	737	85	718	31	736	86	717	32	735	6	681	182	621	128	639	183	620	129	638	184	619	130	637	104																												
765	41	726	95	708	40	727	94	709	39	728	93	710	20	667	139	628	193	610	138	629	192	611	137	630	191	612	118																												
759	755	48	701	66	754	49	700	67	753	50	699	68	26	661	657	146	603	164	656	147	602	165	655	148	601	166	124																												
25	690	77	744	59	691	76	745	58	692	75	746	57	760	123	592	175	646	157	593	174	647	156	594	173	648	155	662																												
761	87	716	33	734	88	715	34	733	89	714	35	732	24	663	185	618	131	636	186	617	132	635	187	616	133	634	122																												
23	38	729	92	711	37	730	91	712	36	731	90	713	762	121	136	631	190	613	135	632	189	614	134	633	188	615	664																												
763	752	51	698	69	751	52	697	70	750	53	696	71	22	665	654	149	600	167	653	150	599	168	652	151	598	169	120																												
21	693	74	747	56	694	73	748	55	695	72	749	54	764	119	595	172	649	154	596	171	650	153	597	170	651	152	666																												
13	777	9	775	11	773	1	778	15	769	17	767	19	771	111	679	107	677	109	675	99	680	113	671	115	669	117	673																												
308	302	482	304	480	306	490	301	476	310	474	312	472	478	210	204	580	206	578	208	588	203	574	212	572	214	570	576																												
489	321	457	456	449	328	344	322	458	455	450	327	343	296	587	223	555	554	547	230	246	224	556	553	548	229	245	198																												
297	440	352	432	353	361	417	439	351	431	354	362	418	488	199	538	254	530	255	263	515	537	253	529	256	264	516	586																												
487	416	409	377	384	400	369	415	410	378	383	399	370	298	585	514	507	279	286	498	271	513	508	280	285	497	272	200																												
299	392	376	401	408	385	393	391	375	402	407	386	394	486	201	294	278	499	506	287	491	293	277	500	505	288	492	584																												
485	345	424	360	425	433	368	346	423	359	426	434	367	300	583	247	522	262	523	531	270	248	521	261	524	532	269	202																												
471	441	337	329	336	448	464	442	338	330	335	447	463	314	569	539	239	231	238	546	562	540	240	232	237	545	561	216																												
465	323	459	454	451	326	342	324	460	453	452	325	341	320	563	225	557	552	549	228	244	226	558	551	550	227	243	222																												
319	438	350	430	355	363	419	437	349	429	356	364	420	466	221	536	252	528	257	265	517	535	251	527	258	266	518	564																												
467	414	411	379	382	398	371	413	412	380	381	397	372	318	565	512	509	281	284	496	273	511	510	282	283	495	274	220																												
317	390	374	403	406	387	395	389	373	404	405	388	396	468	219	292	276	501	504	289	493	291	275	502	503	290	494	566																												
469	347	422	358	427	435	366	348	421	357	428	436	365	316	567	249	520	260	525	533	268	250	519	259	526	534	267	218																												
315	443	339	331	334	446	462	444	340	332	333	445	461	470	217	541	241	233	236	544	560	542	242	234	235	543	559	568																												
307	483	303	481	305	479	295	484	309	475	311	473	313	477	209	581	205	579	207	577	197	582	211	573	213	571	215	575																												
Inder J. Taneja														https://inderjtaneja.com/														https://numbers-magic.com/														@NumbersMagic													

51.

14	8	776	10	774	12	784	7	770	16	768	18	766	772	112	106	678	108	676	110	686	105	672	114	670	116	668	674																												
783	748	757	29	755	31	27	48	738	46	740	44	747	2	685	650	659	127	657	129	125	146	640	144	642	142	649	100																												
3	42	727	722	64	720	66	62	52	734	50	728	743	782	101	140	629	624	162	622	164	160	150	636	148	630	645	684																												
781	41	61	74	68	716	718	705	79	707	73	724	744	4	683	139	159	172	166	618	620	607	177	609	171	626	646	102																												
5	745	725	71	700	698	83	704	84	86	714	60	40	780	103	647	627	169	602	600	181	606	182	184	616	158	138	682																												
779	746	59	72	82	97	690	91	692	703	713	726	39	6	681	648	157	170	180	195	592	189	594	605	615	628	137	104																												
765	753	732	77	88	92	691	98	689	697	708	53	32	20	667	655	634	175	186	190	593	196	591	599	610	151	130	118																												
759	742	49	715	90	694	93	688	95	695	70	736	43	26	661	644	147	617	188	596	191	590	193	597	168	638	141	124																												
25	36	729	710	696	687	96	693	94	89	75	56	749	760	123	134	631	612	598	589	194	595	192	187	173	154	651	662																												
761	35	55	709	699	87	702	81	701	85	76	730	750	24	663	133	153	611	601	185	604	179	603	183	174	632	652	122																												
23	751	731	712	717	69	67	80	706	78	711	54	34	762	121	653	633	614	619	167	165	178	608	176	613	152	132	664																												
763	33	57	63	721	65	719	723	733	51	735	58	752	22	665	131	155	161	623	163	621	625	635	149	637	156	654	120																												
21	38	28	756	30	754	758	737	47	739	45	741	37	764	119	136	126	658	128	656	660	639	145	641	143	643	135	666																												
13	777	9	775	11	773	1	778	15	769	17	767	19	771	111	679	107	677	109	675	99	680	113	671	115	669	117	673																												
308	302	482	304	480	306	490	301	476	310	474	312	472	478	210	204	580	206	578	208	588	203	574	212	572	214	570	576																												
489	351	436	345	438	368	362	422	424	411	373	413	367	296	587	277	526	223	544	278	525	224	543	279	524	225	542	198																												
297	346	437	352	435	365	406	404	377	410	378	380	420	488	199	240	527	294	509	239	528	293	510	238	529	292	511	586																												
487	440	347	434	349	366	376	391	396	385	398	409	419	298	585	562	241	508	259	561	242	507	260	560	243	506	261	200																												
299	433	350	439	348	371	382	386	397	392	395	403	414	486	201	491	276	545	258	492	275	546	257	493	274	547	256	584																												
485	359	428	353	430	421	384	400	387	394	389	401	364	300	583	280	523	226	541	281	522	227	540	282	521	228	539	202																												
471	354	429	360	427	416	402	393	390	399	388	383	369	314	569	237	530	291	512	236	531	290	513	235	532	289	514	216																												
465	432	355	426	357	415	405	381	408	375	407	379	370	320	563	559	244	505	262	558	245	504	263	557	246	503	264	222																												
319	425	358	431	356	418	423	363	361	374	412	372	417	466	221	494	273	548	255	495	272	549	254	496	271	550	253	564																												
467	327	460	321	462	335	452	329	454	343	444	337	446	318	565	283	520	229	538	284	519	230	537	285	518	231	536	220																												
317	322	461	328	459	330	453	336	451	338	445	344	443	468	219	234	533	288	515	233	534	287	516	232	535	286	517	566																												
469	464	323	458	325	456	331	450	333	448	339	442	341	316	567	556	247	502	265	555	248	501	266	554	249	500	267	218																												
315	457	326	463	324	449	334	455	332	441	342	447	340	470	217	497	270	551	252	498	269	552	251	499	268	553	250	568																												
307	483	303	481	305	479	295	484	309	475	311	473	313	477	209	581	205	579	207	577	197	582	211	573	213	571	215	575																												
Inder J. Taneja														https://inderjtaneja.com/														https://numbers-magic.com/														@NumbersMagic													

76.

546	193	243	264	214	567	526	220	573	588	235	541	8	2	782	784	771	13	773	7	40	34	750	752	739	45	741	39
195	242	545	566	263	216	572	525	222	237	540	587	5	766	764	17	770	18	20	780	37	734	732	49	738	50	52	748
241	547	194	215	568	262	221	574	524	539	589	236	6	16	31	756	25	758	769	779	38	48	63	724	57	726	737	747
579	226	532	535	229	582	249	199	552	561	208	258	11	22	26	757	32	755	763	774	43	54	58	725	64	723	731	742
228	531	578	581	534	231	551	248	201	210	257	560	781	24	760	27	754	29	761	4	749	56	728	59	722	61	729	36
530	580	227	230	583	533	200	553	247	256	562	209	776	762	753	30	759	28	23	9	744	730	721	62	727	60	55	41
259	565	212	197	550	244	239	592	542	521	571	218	775	765	21	768	15	767	19	10	743	733	53	736	47	735	51	42
213	260	563	548	245	198	590	543	240	219	522	569	778	783	3	1	14	772	12	777	746	751	35	33	46	740	44	745
564	211	261	246	196	549	544	238	591	570	217	523	343	444	337	446	351	436	345	438	72	66	718	720	707	77	709	71
536	586	233	224	577	527	206	559	253	250	556	203	338	445	344	443	346	437	352	435	69	702	700	81	706	82	84	716
234	537	584	575	528	225	557	254	207	204	251	554	448	339	442	341	440	347	434	349	70	80	95	692	89	694	705	715
585	232	538	529	223	576	255	205	558	555	202	252	441	342	447	340	433	350	439	348	75	86	90	693	96	691	699	710
168	162	622	624	611	173	613	167	359	428	353	430	367	420	361	422	375	412	369	414	717	88	696	91	690	93	697	68
165	606	604	177	610	178	180	620	354	429	360	427	362	421	368	419	370	413	376	411	712	698	689	94	695	92	87	73
166	176	191	596	185	598	609	619	432	355	426	357	424	363	418	365	416	371	410	373	711	701	85	704	79	703	83	74
171	182	186	597	192	595	603	614	425	358	431	356	417	366	423	364	409	374	415	372	714	719	67	65	78	708	76	713
621	184	600	187	594	189	601	164	383	404	377	406	391	396	385	398	474	265	315	336	286	495	454	292	501	516	307	469
616	602	593	190	599	188	183	169	378	405	384	403	386	397	392	395	267	314	473	494	335	288	500	453	294	309	468	515
615	605	181	608	175	607	179	170	408	379	402	381	400	387	394	389	313	475	266	287	496	334	293	502	452	467	517	308
618	623	163	161	174	612	172	617	401	382	407	380	393	390	399	388	507	298	460	463	301	510	321	271	480	489	280	330
136	130	654	656	643	141	645	135	104	98	686	688	675	109	677	103	300	459	506	509	462	303	479	320	273	282	329	488
133	638	636	145	642	146	148	652	101	670	668	113	674	114	116	684	458	508	299	302	511	461	272	481	319	328	490	281
134	144	159	628	153	630	641	651	102	112	127	660	121	662	673	683	331	493	284	269	478	316	311	520	470	449	499	290
139	150	154	629	160	627	635	646	107	118	122	661	128	659	667	678	285	332	491	476	317	270	518	471	312	291	450	497
653	152	632	155	626	157	633	132	685	120	664	123	658	125	665	100	492	283	333	318	268	477	472	310	519	498	289	451
648	634	625	158	631	156	151	137	680	666	657	126	663	124	119	105	464	514	305	296	505	455	278	487	325	322	484	275
647	637	149	640	143	639	147	138	679	669	117	672	111	671	115	106	306	465	512	503	456	297	485	326	279	276	323	482
650	655	131	129	142	644	140	649	682	687	99	97	110	676	108	681	513	304	466	457	295	504	327	277	486	483	274	324
Inder J. Taneja							https://inderjtaneja.com/							https://numbers-magic.com/							@NumbersMagic						

101.

8	2	782	784	771	13	773	7	263	524	257	526	40	34	750	752	739	45	741	39	72	66	718	720	707	77	709	71
5	766	764	17	770	18	20	780	258	525	264	523	37	734	732	49	738	50	52	748	69	702	700	81	706	82	84	716
6	16	31	756	25	758	769	779	528	259	522	261	38	48	63	724	57	726	737	747	70	80	95	692	89	694	705	715
11	22	26	757	32	755	763	774	521	262	527	260	43	54	58	725	64	723	731	742	75	86	90	693	96	691	699	710
781	24	760	27	754	29	761	4	271	516	265	518	749	56	728	59	722	61	729	36	717	88	696	91	690	93	697	68
776	762	753	30	759	28	23	9	266	517	272	515	744	730	721	62	727	60	55	41	712	698	689	94	695	92	87	73
775	765	21	768	15	767	19	10	520	267	514	269	743	733	53	736	47	735	51	42	711	701	85	704	79	703	83	74
778	783	3	1	14	772	12	777	513	270	519	268	746	751	35	33	46	740	44	745	714	719	67	65	78	708	76	713
311	476	305	478	319	468	313	470	454	463	323	461	325	321	342	444	340	446	338	453	104	98	686	688	675	109	677	103
306	477	312	475	314	469	320	467	336	343	406	427	355	441	414	378	392	370	399	449	101	670	668	113	674	114	116	684
480	307	474	309	472	315	466	317	335	385	354	379	351	396	423	440	368	422	407	450	102	112	127	660	121	662	673	683
473	310	479	308	465	318	471	316	451	412	438	365	393	429	390	417	356	344	381	334	107	118	122	661	128	659	667	678
232	226	558	560	547	237	549	231	452	437	430	352	376	363	359	384	401	408	415	333	685	120	664	123	658	125	665	100
229	542	540	241	546	242	244	556	459	380	413	358	432	387	411	346	439	395	364	326	680	666	657	126	663	124	119	105
230	240	255	532	249	534	545	555	448	361	372	404	419	350	398	425	377	436	383	337	679	669	117	672	111	671	115	106
235	246	250	533	256	531	539	550	330	416	391	400	367	362	435	409	424	373	348	455	682	687	99	97	110	676	108	681
557	248	536	251	530	253	537	228	329	394	349	433	388	405	382	371	420	357	426	456	287	500	281	502	279	508	273	510
552	538	529	254	535	252	247	233	457	369	375	386	434	418	347	402	403	431	360	328	282	501	288	499	274	509	280	507
551	541	245	544	239	543	243	234	327	428	397	421	410	374	366	353	345	389	442	458	504	283	498	285	512	275	506	277
554	559	227	225	238	548	236	553	332	322	462	324	460	464	443	341	445	339	447	331	497	286	503	284	505	278	511	276
200	194	590	592	579	205	581	199	168	162	622	624	611	173	613	167	303	484	297	486	136	130	654	656	643	141	645	135
197	574	572	209	578	210	212	588	165	606	604	177	610	178	180	620	298	485	304	483	133	638	636	145	642	146	148	652
198	208	223	564	217	566	577	587	166	176	191	596	185	598	609	619	488	299	482	301	134	144	159	628	153	630	641	651
203	214	218	565	224	563	571	582	171	182	186	597	192	595	603	614	481	302	487	300	139	150	154	629	160	627	635	646
589	216	568	219	562	221	569	196	621	184	600	187	594	189	601	164	295	492	289	494	653	152	632	155	626	157	633	132
584	570	561	222	567	220	215	201	616	602	593	190	599	188	183	169	290	493	296	491	648	634	625	158	631	156	151	137
583	573	213	576	207	575	211	202	615	605	181	608	175	607	179	170	496	291	490	293	647	637	149	640	143	639	147	138
586	591	195	193	206	580	204	585	618	623	163	161	174	612	172	617	489	294	495	292	650	655	131	129	142	644	140	649
Inder J. Taneja							https://inderjtaneja.com/							https://numbers-magic.com/							@NumbersMagic						

126.

7	780	1	782	15	772	9	774	23	764	17	766	31	756	25	758	39	748	33	750	47	740	41	742	55	732	49	734
2	781	8	779	10	773	16	771	18	765	24	763	26	757	32	755	34	749	40	747	42	741	48	739	50	733	56	731
784	3	778	5	776	11	770	13	768	19	762	21	760	27	754	29	752	35	746	37	744	43	738	45	736	51	730	53
777	6	783	4	769	14	775	12	761	22	767	20	753	30	759	28	745	38	751	36	737	46	743	44	729	54	735	52
191	596	185	598	583	578	208	576	210	206	196	590	194	584	533	528	258	526	260	256	246	540	244	534	63	724	57	726
186	597	192	595	205	239	550	211	570	231	558	219	562	580	255	289	500	261	520	281	508	269	512	530	58	725	64	723
600	187	594	189	581	214	567	242	547	222	559	234	555	204	531	264	517	292	497	272	509	284	505	254	728	59	722	61
593	190	599	188	203	574	215	546	235	566	223	554	227	582	253	524	265	496	285	516	273	504	277	532	721	62	727	60
183	604	177	606	588	543	238	571	218	551	230	563	226	197	538	493	288	521	268	501	280	513	276	247	71	716	65	718
178	605	184	603	193	240	549	212	569	232	557	220	561	592	243	290	499	262	519	282	507	270	511	542	66	717	72	715
608	179	602	181	585	213	568	241	548	221	560	233	556	200	535	263	518	291	498	271	510	283	506	250	720	67	714	69
601	182	607	180	199	573	216	545	236	565	224	553	228	586	249	523	266	495	286	515	274	503	278	536	713	70	719	68
175	612	169	614	587	544	237	572	217	552	229	564	225	198	537	494	287	522	267	502	279	514	275	248	79	708	73	710
170	613	176	611	201	207	577	209	575	579	589	195	591	202	251	257	527	259	525	529	539	245	541	252	74	709	80	707
616	171	610	173	433	428	358	426	360	356	346	440	344	434	483	478	308	476	310	306	296	490	294	484	712	75	706	77
609	174	615	172	355	389	400	361	420	381	408	369	412	430	305	339	450	311	470	331	458	319	462	480	705	78	711	76
167	620	161	622	431	364	417	392	397	372	409	384	405	354	481	314	467	342	447	322	459	334	455	304	87	700	81	702
162	621	168	619	353	424	365	396	385	416	373	404	377	432	303	474	315	446	335	466	323	454	327	482	82	701	88	699
624	163	618	165	438	393	388	421	368	401	380	413	376	347	488	443	338	471	318	451	330	463	326	297	704	83	698	85
617	166	623	164	343	390	399	362	419	382	407	370	411	442	293	340	449	312	469	332	457	320	461	492	697	86	703	84
159	628	153	630	435	363	418	391	398	371	410	383	406	350	485	313	468	341	448	321	460	333	456	300	95	692	89	694
154	629	160	627	349	423	366	395	386	415	374	403	378	436	299	473	316	445	336	465	324	453	328	486	90	693	96	691
632	155	626	157	437	394	387	422	367	402	379	414	375	348	487	444	337	472	317	452	329	464	325	298	696	91	690	93
625	158	631	156	351	357	427	359	425	429	439	345	441	352	301	307	477	309	475	479	489	295	491	302	689	94	695	92
151	636	145	638	143	644	137	646	135	652	129	654	127	660	121	662	119	668	113	670	111	676	105	678	103	684	97	686
146	637	152	635	138	645	144	643	130	653	136	651	122	661	128	659	114	669	120	667	106	677	112	675	98	685	104	683
640	147	634	149	648	139	642	141	656	131	650	133	664	123	658	125	672	115	666	117	680	107	674	109	688	99	682	101
633	150	639	148	641	142	647	140	649	134	655	132	657	126	663	124	665	118	671	116	673	110	679	108	681	102	687	100
Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@NumbersMagic															

151.

676	674	107	680	108	110	658	656	125	662	126	128	63	724	57	726	604	602	179	608	180	182	586	584	197	590	198	200		
106	121	666	115	668	679	124	139	648	133	650	661	58	725	64	723	178	193	594	187	596	607	196	211	576	205	578	589		
112	116	667	122	665	673	130	134	649	140	647	655	728	59	722	61	184	188	595	194	593	601	202	206	577	212	575	583		
114	670	117	664	119	671	132	652	135	646	137	653	721	62	727	60	186	598	189	592	191	599	204	580	207	574	209	581		
672	663	120	669	118	113	654	645	138	651	136	131	71	716	65	718	600	591	192	597	190	185	582	573	210	579	208	203		
675	111	678	105	677	109	657	129	660	123	659	127	66	717	72	715	603	183	606	177	605	181	585	201	588	195	587	199		
622	620	161	626	162	164	640	638	143	644	144	146	720	67	714	69	550	548	233	554	234	236	568	566	215	572	216	218		
160	175	612	169	614	625	142	157	630	151	632	643	713	70	719	68	232	247	540	241	542	553	214	229	558	223	560	571		
166	170	613	176	611	619	148	152	631	158	629	637	79	708	73	710	238	242	541	248	539	547	220	224	559	230	557	565		
168	616	171	610	173	617	150	634	153	628	155	635	74	709	80	707	240	544	243	538	245	545	222	562	225	556	227	563		
618	609	174	615	172	167	636	627	156	633	154	149	712	75	706	77	546	537	246	543	244	239	564	555	228	561	226	221		
621	165	624	159	623	163	639	147	642	141	641	145	705	78	711	76	549	237	552	231	551	235	567	219	570	213	569	217		
7	780	1	782	15	772	9	774	23	764	17	766	31	756	25	758	39	748	33	750	47	740	41	742	55	732	49	734		
2	781	8	779	10	773	16	771	18	765	24	763	26	757	32	755	34	749	40	747	42	741	48	739	50	733	56	731		
784	3	778	5	776	11	770	13	768	19	762	21	760	27	754	29	752	35	746	37	744	43	738	45	736	51	730	53		
777	6	783	4	769	14	775	12	761	22	767	20	753	30	759	28	745	38	751	36	737	46	743	44	729	54	735	52		
460	458	323	464	324	326	442	440	341	446	342	344	87	700	81	702	532	530	251	536	252	254	514	512	269	518	270	272		
322	337	450	331	452	463	340	355	432	349	434	445	82	701	88	699	250	265	522	259	524	535	268	283	504	277	506	517		
328	332	451	338	449	457	346	350	433	356	431	439	704	83	698	85	256	260	523	266	521	529	274	278	505	284	503	511		
330	454	333	448	335	455	348	436	351	430	353	437	697	86	703	84	258	526	261	520	263	527	276	508	279	502	281	509		
456	447	336	453	334	329	438	429	354	435	352	347	95	692	89	694	528	519	264	525	262	257	510	501	282	507	280	275		
459	327	462	321	461	325	441	345	444	339	443	343	90	693	96	691	531	255	534	249	533	253	513	273	516	267	515	271		
406	404	377	410	378	380	424	422	359	428	360	362	696	91	690	93	478	476	305	482	306	308	496	494	287	500	288	290		
376	391	396	385	398	409	358	373	414	367	416	427	689	94	695	92	304	319	468	313	470	481	286	301	486	295	488	499		
382	386	397	392	395	403	364	368	415	374	413	421	103	684	97	686	310	314	469	320	467	475	292	296	487	302	485	493		
384	400	387	394	389	401	366	418	369	412	371	419	98	685	104	683	312	472	315	466	317	473	294	490	297	484	299	491		
402	393	390	399	388	383	420	411	372	417	370	365	688	99	682	101	474	465	318	471	316	311	492	483	300	489	298	293		
405	381	408	375	407	379	423	363	426	357	425	361	681	102	687	100	477	309	480	303	479	307	495	291	498	285	497	289		
Inder J. Taneja						https://inderjtaneja.com/						https://numbers-magic.com/						@NumbersMagic											

176.

670	679	107	677	109	105	126	660	124	662	122	669	63	724	57	726	598	607	179	605	181	177	198	588	196	590	194	597
120	649	644	142	642	144	140	130	656	128	650	665	58	725	64	723	192	577	572	214	570	216	212	202	584	200	578	593
119	139	173	616	145	636	165	624	153	628	646	666	728	59	722	61	191	211	245	544	217	564	237	552	225	556	574	594
667	647	148	633	176	613	156	625	168	621	138	118	721	62	727	60	595	575	220	561	248	541	228	553	240	549	210	190
668	137	640	149	612	169	632	157	620	161	648	117	71	716	65	718	596	209	568	221	540	241	560	229	548	233	576	189
675	654	609	172	637	152	617	164	629	160	131	110	66	717	72	715	603	582	537	244	565	224	545	236	557	232	203	182
664	127	174	615	146	635	166	623	154	627	658	121	720	67	714	69	592	199	246	543	218	563	238	551	226	555	586	193
114	651	147	634	175	614	155	626	167	622	134	671	713	70	719	68	186	579	219	562	247	542	227	554	239	550	206	599
113	133	639	150	611	170	631	158	619	162	652	672	79	708	73	710	185	205	567	222	539	242	559	230	547	234	580	600
673	653	610	171	638	151	618	163	630	159	132	112	74	709	80	707	601	581	538	243	566	223	546	235	558	231	204	184
111	135	141	643	143	641	645	655	129	657	136	674	712	75	706	77	183	207	213	571	215	569	573	583	201	585	208	602
116	106	678	108	676	680	659	125	661	123	663	115	705	78	711	76	188	178	606	180	604	608	587	197	589	195	591	187
7	780	1	782	15	772	9	774	23	764	17	766	31	756	25	758	39	748	33	750	47	740	41	742	55	732	49	734
2	781	8	779	10	773	16	771	18	765	24	763	26	757	32	755	34	749	40	747	42	741	48	739	50	733	56	731
784	3	778	5	776	11	770	13	768	19	762	21	760	27	754	29	752	35	746	37	744	43	738	45	736	51	730	53
777	6	783	4	769	14	775	12	761	22	767	20	753	30	759	28	745	38	751	36	737	46	743	44	729	54	735	52
454	463	323	461	325	321	342	444	340	446	338	453	87	700	81	702	526	535	251	533	253	249	270	516	268	518	266	525
336	343	406	427	355	441	414	378	392	370	399	449	82	701	88	699	264	271	478	499	283	513	486	306	320	298	471	521
335	385	354	379	351	396	423	440	368	422	407	450	704	83	698	85	263	313	282	307	279	468	495	512	296	494	479	522
451	412	438	365	393	429	390	417	356	344	381	334	697	86	703	84	523	484	510	293	465	501	318	489	284	272	309	262
452	437	430	352	376	363	359	384	401	408	415	333	95	692	89	694	524	509	502	280	304	291	287	312	473	480	487	261
459	380	413	358	432	387	411	346	439	395	364	326	90	693	96	691	531	308	485	286	504	315	483	274	511	467	292	254
448	361	372	404	419	350	398	425	377	436	383	337	696	91	690	93	520	289	300	476	491	278	470	497	305	508	311	265
330	416	391	400	367	362	435	409	424	373	348	455	689	94	695	92	258	488	319	472	295	290	507	481	496	301	276	527
329	394	349	433	388	405	382	371	420	357	426	456	103	684	97	686	257	466	277	505	316	477	310	299	492	285	498	528
457	369	375	386	434	418	347	402	403	431	360	328	98	685	104	683	529	297	303	314	506	490	275	474	475	503	288	256
327	428	397	421	410	374	366	353	345	389	442	458	688	99	682	101	255	500	469	493	482	302	294	281	273	317	514	530
332	322	462	324	460	464	443	341	445	339	447	331	681	102	687	100	260	250	534	252	532	536	515	269	517	267	519	259

Inder J. Taneja

<https://inderjtaneja.com/>

<https://numbers-magic.com/>

@NumbersMagic

201.

634	105	155	176	126	655	614	132	661	676	147	629	63	724	57	726	177	607	606	605	178	182	195	589	588	587	196	200
107	154	633	654	175	128	660	613	134	149	628	675	58	725	64	723	602	184	600	185	187	597	584	202	582	203	205	579
153	635	106	127	656	174	133	662	612	627	677	148	728	59	722	61	596	595	191	192	592	189	578	577	209	210	574	207
667	138	620	623	141	670	161	111	640	649	120	170	721	62	727	60	194	190	593	594	193	591	212	208	575	576	211	573
140	619	666	669	622	143	639	160	113	122	169	648	71	716	65	718	183	598	186	599	601	188	201	580	204	581	583	206
618	668	139	142	671	621	112	641	159	168	650	121	66	717	72	715	603	181	179	180	604	608	585	199	197	198	586	590
171	653	124	109	638	156	151	680	630	609	659	130	720	67	714	69	231	553	552	551	232	236	213	571	570	569	214	218
125	172	651	636	157	110	678	631	152	131	610	657	713	70	719	68	548	238	546	239	241	543	566	220	564	221	223	561
652	123	173	158	108	637	632	150	679	658	129	611	79	708	73	710	542	541	245	246	538	243	560	559	227	228	556	225
624	674	145	136	665	615	118	647	165	162	644	115	74	709	80	707	248	244	539	540	247	537	230	226	557	558	229	555
146	625	672	663	616	137	645	166	119	116	163	642	712	75	706	77	237	544	240	545	547	242	219	562	222	563	565	224
673	144	626	617	135	664	167	117	646	643	114	164	705	78	711	76	549	235	233	234	550	554	567	217	215	216	568	572
7	780	1	782	15	772	9	774	23	764	17	766	31	756	25	758	39	748	33	750	47	740	41	742	55	732	49	734
2	781	8	779	10	773	16	771	18	765	24	763	26	757	32	755	34	749	40	747	42	741	48	739	50	733	56	731
784	3	778	5	776	11	770	13	768	19	762	21	760	27	754	29	752	35	746	37	744	43	738	45	736	51	730	53
777	6	783	4	769	14	775	12	761	22	767	20	753	30	759	28	745	38	751	36	737	46	743	44	729	54	735	52
351	436	345	438	368	362	422	424	411	373	413	367	87	700	81	702	296	290	494	496	483	301	485	295	279	508	273	510
346	437	352	435	365	406	404	377	410	378	380	420	82	701	88	699	293	478	476	305	482	306	308	492	274	509	280	507
440	347	434	349	366	376	391	396	385	398	409	419	704	83	698	85	294	304	319	468	313	470	481	491	512	275	506	277
433	350	439	348	371	382	386	397	392	395	403	414	697	86	703	84	299	310	314	469	320	467	475	486	505	278	511	276
359	428	353	430	421	384	400	387	394	389	401	364	95	692	89	694	493	312	472	315	466	317	473	292	287	500	281	502
354	429	360	427	416	402	393	390	399	388	383	369	90	693	96	691	488	474	465	318	471	316	311	297	282	501	288	499
432	355	426	357	415	405	381	408	375	407	379	370	696	91	690	93	487	477	309	480	303	479	307	298	504	283	498	285
425	358	431	356	418	423	363	361	374	412	372	417	689	94	695	92	490	495	291	289	302	484	300	489	497	286	503	284
327	460	321	462	335	452	329	454	343	444	337	446	103	684	97	686	255	532	249	534	263	524	257	526	271	516	265	518
322	461	328	459	330	453	336	451	338	445	344	443	98	685	104	683	250	533	256	531	258	525	264	523	266	517	272	515
464	323	458	325	456	331	450	333	448	339	442	341	688	99	682	101	536	251	530	253	528	259	522	261	520	267	514	269
457	326	463	324	449	334	455	332	441	342	447	340	681	102	687	100	529	254	535	252	521	262	527	260	513	270	519	268

Inder J. Taneja

<https://inderjtaneja.com/>

<https://numbers-magic.com/>

@NumbersMagic

226.

670	679	107	677	109	105	126	660	124	662	122	669	63	724	57	726	207	580	201	582	224	218	566	568	555	229	557	223
120	649	644	142	642	144	140	130	656	128	650	665	58	725	64	723	202	581	208	579	221	550	548	233	554	234	236	564
119	139	152	146	638	640	627	157	629	151	646	666	728	59	722	61	584	203	578	205	222	232	247	540	241	542	553	563
667	647	149	622	620	161	626	162	164	636	138	118	721	62	727	60	577	206	583	204	227	238	242	541	248	539	547	558
668	137	150	160	175	612	169	614	625	635	648	117	71	716	65	718	215	572	209	574	565	240	544	243	538	245	545	220
675	654	155	166	170	613	176	611	619	630	131	110	66	717	72	715	210	573	216	571	560	546	537	246	543	244	239	225
664	127	637	168	616	171	610	173	617	148	658	121	720	67	714	69	576	211	570	213	559	549	237	552	231	551	235	226
114	651	632	618	609	174	615	172	167	153	134	671	713	70	719	68	569	214	575	212	562	567	219	217	230	556	228	561
113	133	631	621	165	624	159	623	163	154	652	672	79	708	73	710	183	604	177	606	191	596	185	598	199	588	193	590
673	653	634	639	147	145	158	628	156	633	132	112	74	709	80	707	178	605	184	603	186	597	192	595	194	589	200	587
111	135	141	643	143	641	645	655	129	657	136	674	712	75	706	77	608	179	602	181	600	187	594	189	592	195	586	197
116	106	678	108	676	680	659	125	661	123	663	115	705	78	711	76	601	182	607	180	593	190	599	188	585	198	591	196
7	780	1	782	15	772	9	774	23	764	17	766	31	756	25	758	39	748	33	750	47	740	41	742	55	732	49	734
2	781	8	779	10	773	16	771	18	765	24	763	26	757	32	755	34	749	40	747	42	741	48	739	50	733	56	731
784	3	778	5	776	11	770	13	768	19	762	21	760	27	754	29	752	35	746	37	744	43	738	45	736	51	730	53
777	6	783	4	769	14	775	12	761	22	767	20	753	30	759	28	745	38	751	36	737	46	743	44	729	54	735	52
327	460	321	462	335	452	329	454	343	444	337	446	87	700	81	702	255	532	249	534	263	524	257	526	271	516	265	518
322	461	328	459	330	453	336	451	338	445	344	443	82	701	88	699	250	533	256	531	258	525	264	523	266	517	272	515
464	323	458	325	456	331	450	333	448	339	442	341	704	83	698	85	536	251	530	253	528	259	522	261	520	267	514	269
457	326	463	324	449	334	455	332	441	342	447	340	697	86	703	84	529	254	535	252	521	262	527	260	513	270	519	268
368	362	422	424	411	373	413	367	351	436	345	438	95	692	89	694	279	508	273	510	296	290	494	496	483	301	485	295
365	406	404	377	410	378	380	420	346	437	352	435	90	693	96	691	274	509	280	507	293	478	476	305	482	306	308	492
366	376	391	396	385	398	409	419	440	347	434	349	696	91	690	93	512	275	506	277	294	304	319	468	313	470	481	491
371	382	386	397	392	395	403	414	433	350	439	348	689	94	695	92	505	278	511	276	299	310	314	469	320	467	475	486
421	384	400	387	394	389	401	364	359	428	353	430	103	684	97	686	287	500	281	502	493	312	472	315	466	317	473	292
416	402	393	390	399	388	383	369	354	429	360	427	98	685	104	683	282	501	288	499	488	474	465	318	471	316	311	297
415	405	381	408	375	407	379	370	432	355	426	357	688	99	682	101	504	283	498	285	487	477	309	480	303	479	307	298
418	423	363	361	374	412	372	417	425	358	431	356	681	102	687	100	497	286	503	284	490	495	291	289	302	484	300	489
Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@NumbersMagic															

238.

8	2	782	784	771	13	773	7	40	34	750	752	739	45	741	39	271	516	265	518	279	508	273	510	287	500	281	502
5	766	764	17	770	18	20	780	37	734	732	49	738	50	52	748	266	517	272	515	274	509	280	507	282	501	288	499
6	16	31	756	25	758	769	779	38	48	63	724	57	726	737	747	520	267	514	269	512	275	506	277	504	283	498	285
11	22	26	757	32	755	763	774	43	54	58	725	64	723	731	742	513	270	519	268	505	278	511	276	497	286	503	284
781	24	760	27	754	29	761	4	749	56	728	59	722	61	729	36	240	234	550	552	539	245	541	239	295	492	289	494
776	762	753	30	759	28	23	9	744	730	721	62	727	60	55	41	237	534	532	249	538	250	252	548	290	493	296	491
775	765	21	768	15	767	19	10	743	733	53	736	47	735	51	42	238	248	263	524	257	526	537	547	496	291	490	293
778	783	3	1	14	772	12	777	746	751	35	33	46	740	44	745	243	254	258	525	264	523	531	542	489	294	495	292
72	66	718	720	707	77	709	71	343	444	337	446	351	436	345	438	549	256	528	259	522	261	529	236	303	484	297	486
69	702	700	81	706	82	84	716	338	445	344	443	346	437	352	435	544	530	521	262	527	260	255	241	298	485	304	483
70	80	95	692	89	694	705	715	448	339	442	341	440	347	434	349	543	533	253	536	247	535	251	242	488	299	482	301
75	86	90	693	96	691	699	710	441	342	447	340	433	350	439	348	546	551	235	233	246	540	244	545	481	302	487	300
717	88	696	91	690	93	697	68	367	420	361	422	375	412	369	414	359	428	353	430	168	162	622	624	611	173	613	167
712	698	689	94	695	92	87	73	362	421	368	419	370	413	376	411	354	429	360	427	165	606	604	177	610	178	180	620
711	701	85	704	79	703	83	74	424	363	418	365	416	371	410	373	432	355	426	357	166	176	191	596	185	598	609	619
714	719	67	65	78	708	76	713	417	366	423	364	409	374	415	372	425	358	431	356	171	182	186	597	192	595	603	614
223	564	217	566	312	306	478	480	467	317	469	311	391	396	385	398	383	404	377	406	621	184	600	187	594	189	601	164
218	565	224	563	309	462	460	321	466	322	324	476	386	397	392	395	378	405	384	403	616	602	593	190	599	188	183	169
568	219	562	221	310	320	335	452	329	454	465	475	400	387	394	389	408	379	402	381	615	605	181	608	175	607	179	170
561	222	567	220	315	326	330	453	336	451	459	470	393	390	399	388	401	382	407	380	618	623	163	161	174	612	172	617
231	556	225	558	477	328	456	331	450	333	457	308	104	98	686	688	675	109	677	103	136	130	654	656	643	141	645	135
226	557	232	555	472	458	449	334	455	332	327	313	101	670	668	113	674	114	116	684	133	638	636	145	642	146	148	652
560	227	554	229	471	461	325	464	319	463	323	314	102	112	127	660	121	662	673	683	134	144	159	628	153	630	641	651
553	230	559	228	474	479	307	305	318	468	316	473	107	118	122	661	128	659	667	678	139	150	154	629	160	627	635	646
199	588	193	590	207	580	201	582	215	572	209	574	685	120	664	123	658	125	665	100	653	152	632	155	626	157	633	132
194	589	200	587	202	581	208	579	210	573	216	571	680	666	657	126	663	124	119	105	648	634	625	158	631	156	151	137
592	195	586	197	584	203	578	205	576	211	570	213	679	669	117	672	111	671	115	106	647	637	149	640	143	639	147	138
585	198	591	196	577	206	583	204	569	214	575	212	682	687	99	97	110	676	108	681	650	655	131	129	142	644	140	649
Inder J. Taneja								https://inderjtaneja.com/								https://numbers-magic.com/								@NumbersMagic			

3 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation of Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation of numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

References

- [1] **H. White**, Bordered Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/BorderedMagicSquares.html>
- [2] **H. Danielsson**, Bordered Magic Squares - <https://www.magic-squares.info/methods/bordered.html>
- [3] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Types of Multiple Style Magic Squares of Order 28, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2022/05/01/different-types-of-multiple-style-magic-squares-of-order-28/>
- [4] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Types of Multiple Style Magic Squares of Order 28, <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=1391>

• Block-Wise Magic Squares

- [5] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Constructions of Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 8 to 108, May 15, 2019, pp. 1-43, **Zenodo**, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2843326>.
- [6] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Equal Sums Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order $4k$, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-17, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554288>.
- [7] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Rectangles in Construction of Block-Wise Pandiagonal Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-49, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554520>.
- [8] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Equal Sums Magic Squares of Orders $3k$ and $6k$, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554895>.
- [9] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Unequal Sums Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-52, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555260>.
- [10] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 12 to 36, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-53, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555343>.
- [11] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 39 to 45, **Zenodo**, February 2, 2019, pp. 1-73, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555889>.

• Bordered Magic Squares

- [12] **Inder J. Taneja**, Nested Magic Squares With Perfect Square Sums, Pythagorean Triples, and Borders Differences, **Zenodo**, June 14, 2019, pp. 1-59, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3246586>.
- [13] **Inder J. Taneja**, Symmetric Properties of Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, June 29, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3262170>.
- [14] **Inder J. Taneja**, General Sum Symmetric and Positive Entries Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, July 04, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3268877>.
- [15] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares With Order Square Magic Sums, **Zenodo**, January 20, 2020, pp. 1-26, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613690>.
- [16] **Inder J. Taneja**, Fractional and Decimal Type Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2020. **Zenodo**, January 20, 2020, pp.1-25. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613698>.
- [17] **Inder J. Taneja**, Fractional and Decimal Type Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2021, **Zenodo**, December 16, 2020, pp. 1-33, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4327333>.
- [18] **Inder J. Taneja**, Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2022, **Zenodo**, December 28, 2021, pp. 1-38, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5807789>

• **Block-Bordered Magic Squares**

- [19] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - I, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-81, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990291>.
- [20] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - II, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-90, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990293>.
- [21] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - III, **Zenodo**, September 01, 2020, pp. 1-93, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4011213>.

• **Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Squares**

- [22] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic and Bimagic Squares With Magic Sums 21, 21^2 and 2021. **Zenodo**, December 16, 2020, pp. 1-118, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4380343>.
- [23] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 10 to 47. **Zenodo**, January 14, 2021, pp. 1-185, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4437783>.
- [24] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Odd Order Multiples, **Zenodo**, February 10, 2021, pp. 1-75, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4527739>
- [25] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Even Order Multiples, **Zenodo**, February 10, 2021, pp. 1-96, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4527746>

• **Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares**

- [26] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 4, **Zenodo**, August 31, 2021, pp. 1-148, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5347897>.
- [27] **Inder J. Taneja**, Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of Magic and Bordered Magic Squares of Order 6, **Zenodo**, September 10, pp. 1-99 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5500134>.
- [28] **Inder J. Taneja**, Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 8, **Zenodo**, September 17, pp. 1-80, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5514396>.
- [29] **Inder J. Taneja**, Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 10, **Zenodo**, September 17, pp. 1-170, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5514398>.
- [30] **Inder J. Taneja**, Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 12, **Zenodo**, September 23, pp. 1-170, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5523608>.
- [31] **Inder J. Taneja**, Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 14, **Zenodo**, September 26, pp. 1-198, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5528867>.

• **Different Types of Magic Squares**

- [32] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Types of Magic Squares: Even Number Orders From 10 to 26, **Zenodo**, March 26, 2022, pp. 1-167, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6386742>.

- [33] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Types of Magic Squares of Order 28, **Zenodo**, March 26, 2022, pp. 1-115,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6386863>.
- [34] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Types of Magic Squares of Order 30, **Zenodo**, March 26, 2022, pp. 1-123,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6386987>.
- [35] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Types of Magic Squares of Order 32, **Zenodo**, April 04, 2022, pp. 1-77,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6413115>.
- [36] **Inder J. Taneja**, Multiple Style Different Types of Magic Squares of Order 36, **Zenodo**, April 27, 2022,
pp. 1-53, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6499276>,
- [37] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Types of Multiple Style Magic Squares of Order 40, **Zenodo**, April 23, 2022,
pp. 1-85, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6480559>.

• Creative Magic Squares

- [38] **Inder J. Taneja**, Creative Magic Squares: Area Representations, **Zenodo**, June 22, pp. 1-45, 2021,
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5009224>.
-